

TESTING SOFTWARE COMPLEXES FOR DIAGNOSTICS OF RELAY PROTECTION MODELS

Shamsutdinov Kh.F., Pulatov N.K., Akhmadboev M.

[Doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11179353](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11179353)

Annotation: The article presents a model of microprocessor differential protection of a transformer. The structure of the transformer testing software complex, digital processing block diagrams, as well as the results of the operation of the microprocessor current differential protection model for internal and external faults are presented.

Keywords: model, microprocessor, relay, protection, simulation, setpoint, Matlab.

The main advantage of IPCs is that they can only be implemented using a computer and allow testing the protection model at the design stage and testing its functionality using the method of computational experiment.

ANDusee modeling environment MATLAB-Simulink and the Sim Power Systems extension package is the de facto standard for modeling the operating modes of OEO and MTZ [2, 3–4]. A user-friendly interface, ease of creating an OEO model, ample opportunities for visualizing modeling results and exporting them, the ability to create additional custom model blocks, distinguishes this modeling environment from other software packages designed for OEO modeling - PSCAD/EMTDC, EMTP-RV [4], ATP [5], whose operation is based on G. Dommel's algorithms[4].

INAll model blocks included in the library of this extension package have been tested in the laboratories of the Canadian electricity producer, Hydro-Québec, where the correctness of their mathematical description has been confirmed.

TAnother advantage of Sim Power Systems model blocks is that the nominal values of the parameters of the simulated electrical equipment, most of which are available in catalog data, can be used as initial data.

Based on the above, it is advisable to recommend the MATLAB-Simulink modeling environment together with the Sim Power Systems extension package for the development and implementation of PDAs and IPCs with a flexible structure.

Test software package Transformer DIFF. IPC Transformer DIFF “Model of digital differential protection of a power transformer” allows you to study most of the characteristic operating modes of digital differential current protection (DCP) of a power transformer. IPC can be used both to analyze the functioning of existing digital relay protection devices, and to develop and test algorithms for the functioning of new protection devices at the stage of introducing them into production.

Differential protection is protection with absolute selectivity, operating without a time delay and reacting only to damage in the protected area. The operating principle of

differential protection is based on comparing currents from all sides of the protected object.

The Transformer DIFF IPC [7] is developed in MATLAB-Simulink (version R2011b) using the SPS extension package. The block diagram of the model is shown in Fig. 1.

Rice. 1. Structure of the Transformer DIFF IPC in MATLAB-Simulink

The model circuit includes: power supply (Eq system), three-phase power transformer (T), three-phase groups of current transformers on the HV (CT HV) and LV (CT LV) side of the power transformer, digital differential protection (Differential protection), three-phase power switches on the HV (Breaker HV) and LV (Breaker LV) sides of the power transformer, load (Load), blocks for creating a three-phase short-circuit in the coverage area of the DZT (Internal fault 1 and Internal fault 2) and a block for creating a three-phase short-circuit outside the coverage area of the DZT (External fault).

In Fig. Figure 2 shows a block diagram of digital processing of controlled signals - secondary current signals from the HV and LV side of the protected three-phase power transformer. Currents i_{a_HV} , i_{b_HV} , i_{c_HV} – secondary currents of the three-phase CT group located on the HV side of the power transformer; currents i_{a_LV} , i_{b_LV} , i_{c_LV} – secondary currents of the three-phase CT group located on the LV side of the power transformer.

Rice. 2. Block diagram of digital processing of controlled MPTDZ signals

The “Low Pass Filter” (LPF) block contains an active 2nd order low pass filter. The purpose of this analog filter is to suppress spectral components whose frequency exceeds half the sampling frequency. The signal sampling frequency is 1200 Hz.

The “Current Normalization” block brings the secondary currents coming from the output of the ADC block to one basis, i.e., converts these values into o. e. To do this,

the currents on each side are multiplied by normalizing coefficients, which for each side of the power transformer are calculated as follows:

$$K_{HV} = \frac{\sqrt{3} \cdot U_{1nom} \cdot I_{1nom}}{S_{nom} \cdot I_{2nom}},$$

$$K_{LV} = \frac{\sqrt{3} \cdot U_{2nom} \cdot I_{1nom}}{S_{nom} \cdot I_{2nom}} \tag{1}$$

where I1nom and I2nom are the rated primary and secondary current of the CT on the corresponding side of the power transformer.

The “Exclusion I0” block implements the exclusion of the zero-sequence current from the currents of the high side of the power transformer (this operation is applied only in the case of grounding the neutral of the power transformer), for which the currents of the HV side of the power transformer must be multiplied by the coefficient matrix M1 [8]:

$$M_1 = \frac{1}{3} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 2 & -1 & -1 \\ -1 & 2 & -1 \\ -1 & -1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \tag{2}$$

The “Connection group accounting” block compensates for the phase shift between the currents of the LV side of the power transformer and the currents of the HV side. For example, for a simulated power transformer with a Y/Δ-11 connection circuit, the currents on the Δ winding side lead the currents on the Y winding side by 30°. To compensate for the specified phase shift, the currents from the side of the winding connected in Δ must be multiplied by the matrix M2 [8]:

$$M_2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{3}} \cdot \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & -1 \\ -1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \tag{3}$$

The “Differential Current Shaper” block (Formation of differential currents) generates differential (operating) currents for each phase in accordance with the expression [8]:

$$I_{diff} = |i_{HV'} + i_{LV'}|$$

In this case, the direction “towards the protected object” is taken as the positive direction of the current.

In the “Brake current shaper” block (Brake current shaper), the brake currents are generated for each phase according to one of the 8 methods:

$$I_{res} = |i_{HV'}| + |i_{LV'}|$$

In all the above formulas, the operator “| |» corresponds to the operation of calculating the effective value. This operation is performed in the “1st harmonic digital filter” (1 harmonic DF) block. As such a filter, a digital filter is used that implements a single-period discrete Fourier transform, in which the effective value of the fundamental harmonic of the signal $I(n)$ is determined from the samples of the cosine $I^C(n)$ and sine $I^S(n)$ orthogonal components of the input signal [8]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{(n)}^C &= \frac{2}{N} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} i(n) \cos(2\pi n / N); \\
 I_{(n)}^S &= \frac{2}{N} \cdot \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} i(n) \sin(2\pi n / N); \\
 I_{(n)} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cdot \sqrt{(I^C(n))^2 + (I^S(n))^2},
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

where $n = 0 \dots N - 1$ – sample number of the monitored signal in the observation window;

$i(n)$ – input signal samples;

N – number of samples per period of industrial frequency.

At the output of the blocks for each phase, differential I_{a_diff} , I_{b_diff} , I_{c_diff} and braking currents I_{a_res} , I_{b_res} , I_{c_res} are formed, respectively. These currents enter the “Trigger Logic” block, where a command is generated to activate or not operate the protection, based on the specified characteristics of the MTDS, taking into account the presence or absence of a blocking signal.

Rice. 3. Results of the operation of the MPTDZ model for internal damage:

a – trajectory of movement of the operating point; b – graphs of currents I_{diff} and

I_{res}

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